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Tel. No.: 5310-6581/5310-685

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Title:

**Community Awareness of Household Waste
Disposal Practices and their Contribution to
Waterways Pollution in Brgy. 174 Input for
Recommendation**

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Abstract

This study examines the level of community awareness regarding household waste disposal practices and their contribution to waterways pollution in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. Improper waste disposal has been identified as a major environmental issue. Despite the implementation of environmental policies such as Republic Act 9003, improper disposal practices remain evident in many communities.

Using a quantitative research design, the study gathered data from selected households through online survey questionnaires to assess their awareness, practices, and perceptions related to waste disposal. The research focused on key areas including waste segregation, frequency and methods of disposal, environmental awareness, and challenges faced by residents in practicing proper waste management.

Findings indicate that while residents generally demonstrate a moderate to high level of awareness regarding proper waste disposal, there remains a gap between knowledge and actual practices. The study further reveals that household practices significantly contribute to waterways pollution, emphasizing the need for stronger community engagement and education.

The study concludes that awareness alone is insufficient; effective waste management requires stricter policies, accessible facilities, and continuous community education. These findings help guide local governments and organizations in developing targeted, sustainable strategies to reduce pollution and promote environmental responsibility.

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Table of Contents

Title Page

Acknowledgement.....i

Abstract.....ii

Chapter 1 – The Problem and Its Background

Introduction..... 1-2

Background of the Study3

Statement of the Problem4-5

Hypotheses 5

Scope and Delimitation 6

Significance of the Study 6-7

Chapter 2 – Review Of Related Literature

Related Literature and Studies 8-27

Theoretical Framework27-28

Conceptual Framework28-29

Definition of Terms30

**College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource**

Chapter 3 – Methodology

Research Design31-32

Population and sample of The Study.....32-33

Research Instrument 33

Validity of the Research Instrument.....34

Data Gathering Procedure34-35

Statistical Treatment of Data35-38

Chapter 4 – Presentation, Analysis, And Interpretation of Data

Data Interpretation and Analysis39-69

Chapter 5 – Summary, Conclusion, And Recommendations

Summary of Findings70-74

Conclusions74-76

Recommendations77

Bibliography.....78-91

Curriculum Vitae92-96

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Chapter I

The Problem and its Background

Introduction

Water pollution is a growing environmental concern that affects both urban and residential communities, particularly in highly populated cities. Improper waste disposal practices have been identified as one of the major contributors to the degradation of waterways, leading to health risks, flooding, and environmental damage (Cebu Daily News, 2025; WWF-Philippines, 2022). Among these contributors, household waste disposal plays a significant role, as daily activities within homes directly influence the condition of local drainage systems and water sources (Salla & Gosh, 2014).

In Barangay 174 of Caloocan City, households commonly dispose of kitchen waste, leftover food, and used cooking oil through sinks, drains, or nearby canals (Observation, 2026). While these practices may be viewed as normal or convenient, they contribute to clogged drainage, foul odors, and the pollution of local waterways. Similar patterns have been observed in other Philippine communities; for instance, research in coastal barangays of Makati City, Davao Oriental, and in Calamba City, Laguna, found that while residents were aware of proper waste disposal, actual practices often involved dumping, burning, or burying waste, which contributes to environmental pollution and contaminates water sources (Verzosa et al., 2024; Baltazar & Seki, 2020).

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Moreover, improper household waste disposal not only affects the physical condition of waterways but also contributes to broader environmental and social problems. Polluted drainage systems increase the risk of flooding during heavy rains, which can damage homes, disrupt daily activities, and expose residents to waterborne diseases. Accumulated waste in canals also creates breeding grounds for mosquitoes and other pests, posing serious public health concerns within densely populated communities. These impacts highlight that household waste management is not only an environmental issue but also a matter of community safety, health, and sustainable urban living.

Despite existing local ordinances and environmental programs, improper household waste disposal remains evident in the barangay. This situation raises a significant research problem: *“How aware are the residents of Barangay 174 of proper household waste disposal practices, and how do these practices contribute to waterways pollution in their community?”* Understanding this problem is essential in identifying gaps in knowledge and behavior that continue to affect water quality and sanitation at the local level (Triassi et al., 2015; PMC, 2015).

This study will assess the awareness of residents in Barangay 174 regarding household waste disposal practices, identify commonly observed disposal behaviors, and analyze their contribution to waterways pollution. Guided by Sustainable Development Goal 6: Clean Water and Sanitation, the study seeks to provide relevant data that may serve as a basis for community education initiatives, improved waste management strategies, and local policy

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

recommendations aimed at promoting cleaner and safer waterways within the barangay (WWF-Philippines, 2022).

Background of the Study

Water pollution is a serious environmental issue that affects public health, sanitation, and environmental safety, especially in urban communities. One major cause of this problem is improper household waste disposal, where daily domestic waste such as food scraps, plastics, and used cooking oil enters drainage systems and waterways. These practices lead to clogged canals, flooding, foul odors, and water contamination (Kaza et al., 2018).

In the Philippines, improper household waste disposal continues despite the implementation of Republic Act 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act. Several local studies show that although residents are aware of proper waste disposal methods, many still practice improper disposal due to convenience, weak enforcement, and limited facilities (Dela Rosa et al., 2019; Yazawa et al., 2023). These gaps between awareness and actual practice contribute to the continued pollution of waterways and reduce the effectiveness of local waste management programs.

In Barangay 174, Caloocan City, improper household waste disposal remains evident. While some residents may have knowledge of proper waste disposal, actual practices often do not reflect this awareness, similar to findings in other Philippine communities (Baltazar & Seki, 2020). Guided by Sustainable Development Goal 6: Clean Water and Sanitation, this study

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

aims to assess community awareness of household waste disposal practices and describe their contribution to waterways pollution, supporting the principles of good governance and social responsibility (WWF-Philippines, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to examine the relationship between the level of community awareness of household waste disposal practices and the contribution of household waste to waterways pollution. It focuses on how awareness, perception, and household practices influence water pollution in local rivers and other water bodies in Brgy. 174 Camarin Caloocan City.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Role in the in the household (e.g., household head, spouse, child, other member)
 - 1.2 Length of residency in Barangay 174
 - 1.3 Numbers of people living in the household
 - 1.4 Type of residency (house, apartment, rented, informal)
2. What is the level of community Awareness in household waste disposal practices in terms of;

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

- 2.1 Segregation and proper disposal of waste
- 2.2 Frequency and method of waste disposal
- 2.3 Household Practices Contributing to Waterway Pollution
- 2.4 Challenges and Barriers to Proper Waste Disposal
- 2.5 Awareness of environmental impact on waterways
3. Is there a significant relationship on the level of community awareness and household waste disposal practices, when grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of Community Awareness on the Household Practices on their contribution to waterways pollution from the statistical results on SOP 2?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what input for recommendation must propose?

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H_0):

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of community awareness regarding household waste disposal practices and their contribution to waterways pollution in Barangay 174, Caloocan City.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' level of community awareness regarding household waste disposal practices and their contribution to waterways pollution in Barangay 174, Caloocan City.

Scope and Limitations

This study focuses on the community awareness of household waste disposal practices and their contribution to waterways pollution in Barangay 174, Caloocan City. It covers selected households and examines their knowledge, attitudes, and practices in disposing of common household wastes such as plastics, food scraps, used oil, and detergents, and how these affect nearby canals and drainage systems.

The study is limited to household-level waste in Barangay 174 only and excludes industrial, commercial, hazardous, and medical wastes. It does not include water quality testing and relies on survey and interview responses collected during a specific period.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it provides valuable insights into household waste disposal practices and community awareness and their impact on waterways pollution. The findings of this research are expected to benefit:

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Local Community – By understanding the level of awareness and common household practices, residents can be better informed about proper waste disposal and its effect on the environment, encouraging responsible behavior and reducing water pollution.

Policy Makers and Local Government Units (LGUs) – The study provides data that can guide the creation or improvement of policies, programs, and infrastructure for effective household waste management and environmental protection.

Environmental Advocates and Organizations – Non-governmental organizations and environmental groups can use the findings to design targeted educational campaigns and initiatives that raise awareness about the consequences of improper waste disposal on local waterways.

Researchers and Academics – This research contributes to the existing body of knowledge on community waste management, environmental awareness, and pollution, offering a foundation for future studies and interventions in similar communities.

Future Generations – Promoting proper household waste practices today helps protect water resources, maintain healthier ecosystems, and ensure sustainable environmental conditions for the future.

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Chapter II

Review Related Literature and Studies

This chapter contains the review of related literature and studies that support the current research. It provides relevant information and background that help explain and justify the study.

Community Awareness

Community awareness has a significant role in addressing improper waste disposal and waterway pollution. According to Aduana et al. (2024), plastic waste remains is one of the pollutants in Philippine waterways, and that while many residents are aware that plastics harm rivers and marine life, improper disposal practices continue due to limited environmental education and weak enforcement of waste management policies. This suggests that awareness alone is not always enough to change behavior.

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Similarly, Esmael et al. (2025) examined the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of riverside communities in Zamboanga Sibugay. Their findings revealed that although residents understand that throwing garbage into rivers causes pollution, some households still practice improper waste disposal due to convenience and lack of access to proper waste collection systems.

Additionally, improper solid waste disposal is a major contributor to water pollution in rivers and coastal areas. Verzosa et al. (2024) found that in coastal communities in Mati City, waste segregation practices were inconsistent, and household waste often ended up in drainage systems that flow directly into waterways.

It was highlighted that community-based solid waste management programs are important in reducing riverine and coastal pollution Wynne et al. (2020). Their research in Tobacco City demonstrated that when residents are actively involved in waste education programs and river protection campaigns, there is significant reduction in waste entering waterways.

The study aimed to selected urban barangays in Sorsogon to determine how community awareness influenced the handling and disposal of household waste Abao and Pepito (2023) Their findings revealed that while most households possessed high awareness of proper waste segregation and the importance of environmental cleanliness, this knowledge did not always translate into consistent practice. There were many factors such as access to waste collection services, convenience, and socio-economic status that affected whether households implemented proper waste disposal measures.

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Edullantes, Cagurin, and Walag (2024) conducted an impact study on a waste management awareness and livelihood training project in a community near a polluted creek. Their findings showed that combining environmental education with livelihood support encouraged residents to adopt more sustainable waste practices.

Furthermore, Galang (2025) said that high levels of community engagement in local solid waste management programs resulted in improved environmental responsibility. Active participation in community clean-up drives and awareness campaigns strengthened residents' understanding of how improper waste disposal directly affects waterways.

Household waste disposal

According to Fadhullah et al. (2022), household waste disposal practices play a crucial role in maintaining environmental sustainability and reducing pollution in communities. Proper waste segregation, recycling, and responsible disposal help minimize the amount of waste that ends up in landfills and waterways. Households that actively practice segregation were found to significantly reduce environmental contamination and improve municipal waste systems. Because of this, promoting responsible waste disposal at the household level becomes essential in addressing environmental problems.

Effective household waste management practices are essential for reducing environmental pollution and protecting public health. In urban

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

communities, it has been observed that households practicing proper segregation and disposal contribute significantly to waste reduction and environmental conservation. However, inconsistent disposal habits and limited awareness still remain major challenges, as noted by Abegaz et al. (2021), in achieving sustainable waste practices.

Household waste generation has increased significantly due to population growth and urbanization. Studies show that households contribute a large portion of municipal solid waste, making their disposal practices a critical factor in environmental management. When proper methods such as segregation, recycling, and composting are applied, the burden on waste systems can be reduced, as emphasized in global reports by Kaza et al. (2021).

Proper waste disposal practices among households are strongly influenced by environmental awareness and education. Individuals who are knowledgeable about the environmental consequences of improper disposal are more likely to adopt responsible behaviors. Educational programs and community campaigns play a significant role in shaping these practices, particularly in developing communities (Zhang et al., 2023).

Community-based waste management initiatives have also been found to improve household waste disposal practices. When organized programs are implemented, residents tend to become more engaged in environmental protection efforts. This leads to better waste segregation and disposal practices, ultimately contributing to reduced pollution and improved sanitation, as observed in community-based studies (Jauculan, 2023).

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Santos et al. (2022) emphasized that proper household waste management practices are essential for achieving sustainable environmental development. Households that actively participate in recycling programs and proper disposal activities contribute significantly to waste reduction and conservation of resources. These efforts not only lessen environmental impact but also promote a culture of sustainability.

Household waste disposal practices are closely linked to environmental protection and public health outcomes. Improper disposal can lead to contamination of water bodies, spread of diseases, and environmental degradation. As highlighted by the United Nations Environment Programme (2021), promoting responsible waste management at the household level is a key strategy in addressing these issues.

Waste segregation at the household level is considered one of the most effective strategies for improving solid waste management systems. By separating biodegradable, recyclable, and residual waste, households can reduce landfill volume and improve recycling efficiency. This approach has been widely recognized as essential for sustainability (Guerrero et al., 2021).

Household waste disposal practices are also influenced by social norms and cultural attitudes toward environmental responsibility. Communities that place strong value on environmental protection are more likely to demonstrate responsible waste management behaviors. This connection between values and behavior has been discussed in studies such as Nguyen et al. (2022).

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Recycling practices among households contribute significantly to reducing the environmental impact of solid waste. Active participation in recycling programs helps decrease landfill waste and conserve natural resources. In fact, reports from the European Environment Agency (2022) highlight how household-level recycling supports broader environmental sustainability.

Proper waste disposal practices also play a critical role in preventing water pollution. When waste is improperly disposed of in open areas or waterways, it contaminates water sources and harms ecosystems. Encouraging responsible waste management is therefore important in protecting water quality (World Bank, 2022).

Government policies and environmental regulations also influence household waste management practices. Communities with well-implemented policies tend to show better compliance among residents. Effective policy enforcement, according to OECD (2021), encourages households to adopt more responsible disposal behaviors.

Urban households generate large quantities of waste due to increased consumption and changing lifestyles. Because of this, proper disposal becomes even more important in managing the growing waste volume. Promoting waste reduction strategies can significantly improve urban waste systems, as discussed by Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata (2021).

Household waste disposal practices are an important part of sustainable community development. When households consistently practice proper segregation and disposal, environmental pollution is reduced and

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sanitation improves. These efforts also support long-term sustainability goals, as emphasized by the United Nations Development Programme (2023).

Segregation and proper disposal

Household waste segregation plays a crucial role in improving waste management and reducing environmental pollution. According to Elmosaad et al. (2023), sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, and education significantly influence recycling and segregation practices among households in the Eastern Region of Saudi Arabia. Their findings showed that individuals with higher educational attainment and those living in urban areas were more likely to practice proper waste segregation and recycling. This suggests that knowledge and access to information contribute to better waste management behavior.

Similarly, Singh and Ghosh (2023) examined public awareness and behavior regarding waste segregation in urban India. Although most respondents were knowledgeable about proper waste segregation, actual practices remained inconsistent due to insufficient waste bins, irregular collection services, and weak enforcement of policies. The study emphasized that awareness alone is not enough and must be supported by proper infrastructure and monitoring systems.

In a broader context, UN-Habitat (2020) highlighted that proper waste segregation at the household level is a key component of effective solid waste management systems. Separating biodegradable, recyclable, and residual waste improves recycling efficiency and helps reduce environmental pollution. The report further stressed that the combination of public education,

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accessible waste collection systems, and strict enforcement is necessary for sustainable waste management.

Kaur and Kaur (2024) also explored factors influencing household waste segregation behavior in an Indian city. Their findings revealed that environmental awareness, knowledge of segregation practices, and perceived ease of implementation significantly affect compliance. Households that were more aware of environmental impacts demonstrated more consistent waste segregation practices.

Moreover, Raphela et al. (2024) investigated the environmental effects of poor waste segregation in peri-urban areas in South Africa. The study found that improper segregation led to landfill overflow, soil contamination, and water pollution, which increased risks to public health. This highlights the serious consequences of ineffective waste management at the household level.

In support of this, Selvakumaran and Wahid (2023) found that lack of proper waste segregation in Segamat, Malaysia resulted in the mixing of recyclable and organic waste, leading to increased landfill loads. This indicates that failure to segregate waste properly reduces recycling potential and worsens waste management problems.

Marseglia et al. (2025) further emphasized that proper source segregation significantly improves recycling efficiency by reducing contamination in recyclable materials and minimizing dependence on landfills. Their findings support the importance of household participation in achieving effective waste management systems.

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Additionally, Trushna et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review on interventions promoting household waste segregation. The study identified that strategies combining education, incentives, and infrastructure were more effective in encouraging proper waste segregation compared to single-approach programs.

Lastly, Zhang, Lee, and Martinez (2024) analyzed behavioral factors influencing household waste segregation in Southeast Asia. Their findings showed that convenience, environmental awareness, and positive attitudes significantly affect compliance. Providing accessible waste bins and continuous education programs was found to improve proper waste disposal practices.

Methods of Waste Disposal

Waste disposal methods play a significant role in managing solid waste and reducing environmental impacts. According to the World Bank (2022), sanitary landfilling remains a widely used method, particularly in developing countries. This method involves the controlled disposal of waste in engineered facilities designed to prevent environmental contamination. Properly managed landfills help reduce risks to public health and the environment compared to unsanitary disposal practices.

Similarly, the United Nations Environment Programme (2021) identified incineration as an alternative waste disposal method that significantly reduces waste volume through high-temperature burning. The study highlighted that while incineration can generate energy, it requires strict emission controls to minimize air pollution and harmful byproducts.

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In addition, recycling continues to be one of the most effective waste management strategies. According to the Environmental Protection Agency (2021), recycling helps conserve natural resources, reduce energy consumption, and minimize the amount of waste sent to landfills. However, its success largely depends on proper segregation and active participation from households.

Composting is also recognized as a sustainable waste disposal method. The Food and Agriculture Organization (2020) explained that composting converts organic waste into nutrient-rich material that can improve soil quality. This method also helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions by diverting biodegradable waste from landfills.

Moreover, waste-to-energy technologies have gained increasing attention in recent years. The International Energy Agency (2022) reported that these technologies convert waste into usable energy such as electricity and heat, reducing landfill dependency. Despite its benefits, the study noted that high costs and environmental concerns remain barriers to its widespread adoption.

Furthermore, anaerobic digestion is an efficient method for managing organic waste. According to the European Commission (2020), this process produces biogas and organic fertilizer through the decomposition of waste without oxygen. It is particularly effective for food and agricultural waste management.

On the other hand, improper waste disposal methods such as open dumping continue to pose serious environmental threats. The Asian

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Development Bank (2021) emphasized that open dumping leads to pollution of land, air, and water, as well as increased health risks in communities. This highlights the need for improved waste management practices.

Mechanical Biological Treatment (MBT) is another approach used to enhance waste processing efficiency. According to the European Environment Agency (2020), MBT combines sorting and biological treatment processes to recover recyclable materials and reduce the volume of waste sent to landfills.

In a broader context, waste segregation remains a key factor in the effectiveness of different disposal methods. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources (2020) emphasized that proper segregation at the household level improves recycling efficiency and supports sustainable waste management systems.

Lastly, emerging technologies such as plasma gasification are being explored as advanced waste disposal solutions. The National Renewable Energy Laboratory (2021) explained that this method converts waste into synthetic gas using high-temperature plasma, offering an environmentally friendly alternative, although it remains costly and less accessible.

Waterway Pollution

Waterway pollution is a serious environmental issue, especially in urban areas where improper waste disposal is common. Household waste such as plastics, packaging materials, and other domestic refuse often enters rivers and drainage systems through rainfall and surface runoff. Many studies show that mismanaged household waste is a major contributor to river and

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marine pollution, particularly in developing countries with limited waste management systems. The following literature presents related studies that explain how domestic waste practices affect waterways and why proper waste management and community responsibility are important.

Waterway pollution continues to increase due to improper waste disposal from households, especially in urban areas where waste management systems are limited. According to Alvarez et al. (2020), many communities experience the entry of plastics and domestic waste into rivers and drainage systems through surface runoff, which contributes to environmental degradation and poor water quality.

Plastic waste has become one of the main contributors to water pollution, particularly in developing countries. Borrelle et al. (2020) explained that household plastics such as packaging materials and containers are often mismanaged and eventually reach waterways, affecting aquatic life and human health.

Urban rivers are greatly affected by domestic waste due to high population density and inadequate waste collection services. Improper disposal practices lead to the accumulation of waste in waterways, which, as discussed by van Emmerik and Schwarz (2020), results in blockages, flooding, and contamination.

Microplastics in freshwater systems have become a growing concern as they originate from household waste such as plastics and synthetic materials. These particles enter waterways through drainage systems and are

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difficult to remove, posing risks to aquatic ecosystems, as highlighted by Li et al. (2020).

In many Asian countries, poor solid waste management contributes significantly to river pollution. The Asian Development Bank (2020) reported that household waste that is not properly segregated or collected is often dumped into open areas and waterways, worsening environmental conditions.

Rainfall and surface runoff play an important role in transporting household waste into rivers and canals. According to Kumar et al. (2020), waste left in open areas is easily carried into drainage systems, increasing the level of water pollution in urban communities.

Community behavior is a key factor in waterway pollution since improper disposal practices continue even when people are aware of their negative effects. Rahman et al. (2021) found that convenience and lack of strict enforcement often influence households to dispose of waste improperly.

Urban waterways are commonly polluted by domestic sources such as food waste, plastics, and household chemicals, which reduce water quality and harm aquatic organisms. These pollutants often originate from everyday household activities, as explained by Zhang et al. (2021).

Plastic leakage into the environment remains a major issue, with a large portion coming from households. The OECD (2022) emphasized that improper waste handling allows plastics to enter rivers and eventually reach oceans, contributing to global water pollution.

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

In the Philippines, waterway pollution is closely linked to improper household waste disposal. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR, 2020) noted that waste materials often clog drainage systems and canals, leading to flooding and health risks in communities.

Studies monitoring urban rivers have found that plastic waste is one of the most common pollutants present in waterways. Talavera et al. (2023) observed that much of this waste comes from residential areas where proper waste management practices are not consistently followed.

A significant portion of global waste is not properly managed, leading to pollution of both land and water systems. According to the World Bank (2020), household waste plays a major role in this issue, especially in areas with limited waste management infrastructure.

Improper waste segregation at the household level increases the likelihood of waste entering waterways. Singh et al. (2020) explained that when waste is mixed and not properly handled, it becomes more difficult to manage and more likely to pollute the environment.

Reducing waterway pollution requires active community participation and responsible waste practices. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2021) emphasized that households play a key role in preventing pollution by properly managing and disposing of their waste.

Challenges and Barriers

Abegaz et al. (2021) identified the lack of proper waste collection services as one of the major barriers to effective household waste

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

management. In many developing communities, irregular or unavailable collection systems force households to resort to open dumping or burning. These practices increase environmental pollution and pose serious health risks, highlighting the need for improved infrastructure.

Limited environmental awareness among residents is another major concern. Many households remain unaware of the environmental and health consequences of improper waste disposal, leading to poor segregation and recycling practices. As discussed by Fadhullah et al. (2022), increasing environmental education can significantly improve responsible behavior.

Financial limitations also affect waste disposal practices. In some areas, households do not have access to basic waste management resources such as bins or collection services. This discourages proper segregation and disposal, making it difficult for communities to maintain cleanliness. Providing affordable solutions can help address this issue (Santos et al., 2022).

Rapid urbanization and population growth have contributed to the increasing volume of waste in communities. As waste generation rises, existing systems often struggle to manage it effectively. This leads to improper disposal practices, a challenge widely documented in global studies such as Kaza et al. (2021).

Behavioral factors also play a role in waste management challenges. Habits, attitudes, and convenience often influence how individuals dispose of their waste. Even when aware of environmental issues, some people continue improper practices. Nguyen et al. (2022) emphasized that behavioral change requires continuous education and engagement.

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Another issue is the lack of strict enforcement of waste management policies. When regulations are not properly implemented, residents may not feel compelled to follow proper practices. Strengthening enforcement and monitoring systems can improve compliance (Zhang et al., 2023).

Insufficient infrastructure, such as recycling facilities and proper landfill sites, further complicates waste management. Without accessible facilities, households may resort to improper disposal methods. The United Nations Environment Programme (2021) highlights the importance of investing in infrastructure to support sustainable practices.

Cultural attitudes and social norms also influence waste disposal behavior. In some communities, improper disposal has become normalized due to long-standing habits. Encouraging positive environmental values can help shift these behaviors toward more responsible practices (Guerrero et al., 2021).

Public participation is another key factor. Waste management programs are more effective when residents are actively involved. However, lack of participation remains a challenge in many areas. Community engagement initiatives, as noted by Jauculan (2023), can improve outcomes.

Inadequate dissemination of information also contributes to improper waste disposal. Many residents are not fully informed about waste management policies and guidelines. Providing clear and accessible information can improve compliance (OECD, 2021).

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

Environmental problems such as flooding and water pollution are often linked to improper waste disposal. Waste that is dumped in drainage systems can cause blockages and increase flood risks. Addressing these issues requires both improved practices and greater awareness (World Bank, 2022).

Monitoring also plays an important role in waste management. Without proper systems to track compliance, it becomes difficult to ensure that households follow guidelines. Strengthening monitoring mechanisms can improve program effectiveness (United Nations Development Programme, 2023).

Economic inequality can influence how households manage their waste. Low-income households may prioritize basic needs over environmental practices. Providing accessible services can help bridge this gap and promote better waste management behaviors (European Environment Agency, 2022).

Lastly, lack of coordination between local government units and communities can hinder effective waste management. Successful programs require collaboration between authorities and residents. Strengthening communication and partnerships, as emphasized by the United Nations Environment Programme (2022), can significantly improve outcomes.

Environmental Impact

Recent studies show that improper household waste disposal continues to significantly impact waterways. Household waste such as plastics, packaging, and containers is a major contributor to pollution in rivers and lakes,

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

especially in developing countries, where waste systems are often inadequate (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021). These wastes are commonly transported by runoff or direct dumping, leading to environmental degradation and threats to aquatic life.

Improper waste management remains a global concern. According to the World Bank (2022), a significant portion of waste is still not properly managed, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. This mismanaged waste often ends up in drainage systems and rivers, contributing to flooding and water contamination. As a result, strengthening waste infrastructure and encouraging proper disposal practices are necessary.

Urban rivers also play a critical role in plastic pollution. Plastics tend to accumulate in river systems due to poor household disposal practices, as explained by van Emmerik and Schwarz (2020), making rivers major pathways of waste toward oceans. This accumulation disrupts water flow and harms aquatic ecosystems, emphasizing the need for monitoring and waste reduction.

In Asia, rapid urbanization has worsened the problem of waste leakage into waterways. The Asian Development Bank (2021) highlighted that increasing population density and limited infrastructure contribute to the growing volume of household waste entering rivers and coastal areas. Addressing this issue requires both policy interventions and community-based waste management strategies.

Microplastic pollution is another growing concern linked to household activities. Li et al. (2020) found that microplastics from degraded plastics and

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

synthetic materials are widespread in freshwater systems. These particles are difficult to remove through wastewater treatment processes, allowing them to persist in aquatic environments and pose risks to both wildlife and human health.

Similarly, domestic sources significantly contribute to microplastic contamination, which can carry toxic substances and affect aquatic organisms (Wagner et al., 2021). Reducing plastic consumption and improving treatment technologies are therefore essential in minimizing this type of pollution.

In the Philippine setting, improper household waste disposal has been identified as a major cause of clogged drainage systems and flooding. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources (2021) reported that plastics, food waste, and other domestic materials accumulate in waterways, particularly during heavy rainfall. This highlights the importance of enforcing waste segregation and strengthening local waste management systems.

Plastic waste entering oceans through rivers remains a major environmental issue. It is estimated that millions of tons of plastic are transported annually, largely from areas with poor waste collection systems (Schmidt et al., 2020). Household waste contributes significantly to this problem, indicating the need for improved services and community education.

Human behavior and awareness also play a crucial role in waste management. Improper disposal practices at the household level contribute directly to environmental degradation, especially in areas lacking formal waste systems, as emphasized by UN-Habitat (2020). Increasing awareness and promoting responsible behavior are key to reducing pollution.

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Plastic leakage into the environment continues to rise due to high consumption and improper disposal. According to OECD (2022), rivers act as major pathways for plastic waste, much of which originates from household use. Policy measures and behavioral changes are necessary to address this growing concern.

Without immediate action, plastic pollution in waterways is expected to worsen. Household waste has been identified as a primary source, and solutions such as improving collection systems and promoting recycling are strongly recommended (Pew Charitable Trusts & SYSTEMIQ, 2020). These efforts can significantly reduce waste entering aquatic environments.

Freshwater ecosystems are also threatened by plastic pollution. Improperly disposed household waste breaks down into microplastics, which are ingested by aquatic organisms and disrupt food chains (World Wildlife Fund, 2021). This not only affects biodiversity but also poses risks to human health.

Recent findings confirm that household waste remains a dominant contributor to plastic pollution in both freshwater and marine environments. Jambeck et al. (2021) emphasized that everyday consumption patterns are directly linked to environmental impact, reinforcing the importance of responsible waste management.

Lastly, increasing urbanization has intensified the flow of plastic waste into river systems. Zhang et al. (2023) found that household and municipal waste significantly contribute to pollution, affecting water quality and aquatic

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life. Comprehensive waste management strategies, including source reduction and community education, are essential to mitigate these impacts.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Theory of Planned Behavior developed by Icek Ajzen (1991). The theory explains that human behavior is influenced by three important factors: attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. These factors shape an individual's intention to perform a certain action, which eventually leads to actual behavior.

In the context of environmental management, the theory suggests that individuals who possess positive attitudes toward environmental protection and who perceive social support for responsible behavior are more likely to engage in sustainable practices. When individuals believe that they are capable of performing environmentally responsible actions, they are more inclined to practice proper waste management.

Applied to this study, community awareness regarding the effects of household waste on waterways pollution influences residents' attitudes and perceptions about proper waste disposal. This awareness may encourage households to practice responsible waste segregation, proper disposal methods, and appropriate waste disposal frequency. As a result, these responsible practices can help reduce the contribution of household waste to waterways pollution and promote environmental sustainability within the community.

Conceptual Framework

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The conceptual framework of this study follows the Input–Process–Output (IPO) model. The input includes community awareness and demographic factors. Community awareness refers to the knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of residents regarding the effects of household waste disposal on waterways pollution. Demographic factors such as role in the household, residency, household size, and type of residence may also influence how households manage their waste. These inputs are considered important factors that shape residents’ behavior and decision-making regarding waste disposal practices.

The process stage represents the transformation of these inputs into actual household waste disposal practices. This includes responsible waste segregation, proper disposal methods, and the frequency of waste disposal. Through increased awareness and understanding of the environmental effects of improper waste disposal, residents are more likely to practice responsible waste management within their households. These practices reflect behavioral changes that promote proper waste handling and reduce the likelihood of waste entering nearby waterways and drainage systems.

The output of the framework is the reduction of waterways pollution and the improvement of environmental conditions within the community. Responsible household waste disposal practices can contribute to cleaner waterways and drainage systems, decreased flooding and health risks, and more sustainable waste management practices. These outcomes emphasize the importance of strengthening community awareness and encouraging responsible household behaviors in order to protect waterways and promote environmental sustainability.

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Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

Definition of Terms

Community Awareness – The level of knowledge, understanding, and consciousness of residents regarding environmental issues, including proper waste management and its effects on local waterways. High community awareness can influence better waste disposal practices.

Household Waste – Solid waste generated from daily household activities, including food scraps, plastic packaging, paper, glass, and other domestic materials.

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Segregation of Waste – The process of separating waste into categories such as biodegradable, recyclable, residual, and special waste at the source throwing waste into drains, burning garbage, segregating recyclables, or using designated collection systems.

Water Pollution – The contamination of water bodies such as rivers, canals, and drainage systems due to the presence of harmful substances, including household waste, chemicals, and other pollutants. In this study, water pollution is primarily linked to improper household waste disposal that affects the quality of local waterways.

Chapter III

Research Design and Methodology

Research Design

This study will utilize a quantitative descriptive–correlational research design to examine the relationship between community awareness of household waste disposal practices and their contribution to waterways pollution in Barangay 174, Camarin, Caloocan City.

A research design serves as the overall plan or blueprint that guides the collection, measurement, and analysis of data in a research study. It

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provides a structured framework to ensure that the research problem is effectively addressed and that valid and reliable results are obtained.

This study is descriptive in nature because it aims to determine the level of community awareness regarding proper household waste disposal practices and to describe the common disposal behaviors observed among households. Descriptive research focuses on presenting an accurate profile of characteristics, behaviors, or conditions as they naturally occur without manipulating variables.

Furthermore, this study is correlational because it seeks to determine whether a significant relationship exists between community awareness and household waste disposal practices, as well as their contribution to waterways pollution. Correlational research is used to identify the degree of association between variables without establishing cause-and-effect relationships.

This design is appropriate for the present study because it allows the researchers to gather numerical data through a survey questionnaire, analyze patterns in community awareness and waste disposal practices, and determine whether these variables are significantly related. The descriptive–correlational design also enables the researchers to describe existing conditions while examining relationships among variables within a specific community setting.

Population and Sample of the Study

The population of this study consists of household residents of Barangay 174, Camarin, Caloocan City. These residents represent the

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individuals responsible for managing and disposing of household waste within their respective homes. Since the study focuses on community awareness and household waste disposal practices, the target population includes residents who are knowledgeable about their household's daily waste management activities.

Due to time and resource limitations, the study will involve a sample of fifty (50) household residents selected through purposive sampling. This sampling method was chosen to ensure that the respondents are individuals who can provide relevant and reliable information regarding household waste disposal practices and awareness of waterways pollution. The selected participants may include any household members who are directly involved in waste management within their homes.

The use of purposive sampling allows the researchers to focus on respondents who meet specific criteria relevant to the objectives of the study. Although the sample size is limited to 50 participants, it is considered sufficient to describe the level of community awareness and household waste disposal practices within the selected area of Barangay 174.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a structured online survey questionnaire developed through Google Forms as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was based on the Statement of the Problem and was designed to gather quantitative data regarding the respondents' demographic profile, household waste disposal practices, and level of community awareness on waterways pollution.

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The instrument consisted mainly of close-ended questions. A Likert scale format was used to measure the respondents' level of agreement and frequency of practices, allowing numerical values to be assigned for statistical analysis.

The use of Google Forms enabled efficient data collection, automatic recording of responses, and systematic organization of data into spreadsheets, which facilitated statistical treatment such as frequency distribution, percentage, weighted mean, and correlation analysis.

This method was selected due to its accessibility, convenience for respondents, and effectiveness in collecting quantifiable data suitable for quantitative research design.

Validity of the Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study is a researcher-made questionnaire designed to assess community awareness and household waste disposal practices in Barangay 174, Camarin, Caloocan City. The questionnaire items were carefully developed based on the objectives of the study and relevant literature related to waste management and waterways pollution.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire will be submitted to the research professor for review and evaluation. The professor

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will examine the content, clarity, and relevance of each item to determine whether the questions properly measure the variables of the study. Necessary revisions will be made based on the suggestions and recommendations provided.

The validation process ensures that the questionnaire accurately reflects the purpose of the study and that the questions are understandable to the respondents. Through expert review, the researchers aim to improve the reliability and effectiveness of the instrument before it is administered to the selected participants.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers will select 50 household residents as participants using purposive sampling. This method ensures that the respondents are individuals who can provide relevant and reliable information about household waste disposal practices and community awareness regarding waterway pollution.

Data will be collected using an online survey questionnaire created through Google Forms. The questionnaire is designed to gather information regarding the respondents' demographic profile, household waste disposal practices, level of community awareness, and perceived contribution of household waste to waterways pollution. Close-ended questions using a Likert scale will measure the respondents' awareness and disposal practices, while selected open-ended questions will allow respondents to provide additional insights and suggestions.

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The questionnaire link will be distributed to the respondents through online platforms such as social media and messaging applications. The purpose of the study will be explained, and informed consent will be obtained to ensure voluntary participation and confidentiality.

All collected responses will be automatically recorded and compiled by Google Forms, allowing the researchers to efficiently organize and monitor the data. The responses will then be prepared for analysis using appropriate statistical and thematic methods to identify patterns, trends, and insights related to community awareness and household waste disposal practices contributing to waterways pollution.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected from the 50 respondents using survey questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The demographic profile of the respondents was analyzed using frequency and percentage. Frequency shows the number of respondents. This method was applied to variables such as role in the household, length of residency, number of household members, and type of residency.

Weighted mean is used for each item scored using a four-point Likert scale providing an average score for each item as well as the overall section.

To examine the relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their awareness on waste disposal practices that contribute to waterways pollution, the Chi-Square test was employed. A 0.05 level of significance was used to test whether the relationship was real or occurred by

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chance.

Formulas:

Percentage (%)

$$P = (f / N) \times 100$$

Where:

P = Percentage

F = Frequency of responses

N = Total number of respondents

Weighted mean (Mw)

The weighted mean was used to determine the respondents' level of community awareness on household waste disposal practices in terms of;

- (1) Segregation and proper disposal of waste
- (2) Frequency and method of waste disposal
- (3) Household Practices Contributing to Waterway Pollution
- (4) Challenges and Barriers to Proper Waste Disposal
- (5) Awareness of environmental impact on waterways

Where:

f = frequency of each response

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w = weight of each response option

n = 50 respondents

The four point likert scale was interpreted as follow:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Very High Awareness / Strongly Agree
3	2.50 - 3.24	High Awareness / Agree
2	1.75 - 2.49	Low Awareness / Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.74	Very Low Awareness / Strongly Disagree

Chi-square Test

$$\chi^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$$

Where:

$$\chi^2 = \text{Chi-Square value}$$

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

Σ = Summation of all cells

CHAPTER IV

Data Interpretation and Analysis

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the respondents on Community Awareness of Household Waste Disposal Practices and their Contribution to Waterways Pollution in

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Barangay 174. The findings are discussed based on the study’s statement of the problem.

Table 1.1

Profile of the Respondents according to their Role in the Household

Role in the household	Frequency	Percentage
Head of the household	15	29.4%
Spouse	9	17.6%
Child	27	52.9%
Other	0	0%

Table 1.1 shows that 15 respondents, or 29.4%, are heads of the household. This suggests that a considerable portion of the participants are directly involved in managing household decisions, including waste disposal practices. As primary decision-makers, they are more likely to influence how waste is handled, from segregation to disposal methods.

On the other hand, 9 respondents or 17.6% are identified as spouses. Although they may not always be the main decision-makers, spouses still play an important role in maintaining household routines. Their involvement in

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daily activities, such as managing domestic tasks, can significantly affect how waste is handled within the household.

Meanwhile, the largest group consists of children, with 27 respondents or 52.9%. This indicates that more than half of the respondents are younger household members who may not be directly responsible for decision-making. However, they are still actively involved in everyday practices, including waste disposal. Their responses provide insight into how waste-related behaviors are carried out at the household level.

Overall, the data shows that while most respondents are not the primary decision-makers, they are still part of the household system where waste disposal practices are implemented. The presence of both decision-makers and other members allows for a broader understanding of how these practices are observed and carried out within the home.

Table 1.2

Profile of the Respondents according to their Year of Residency

Year of Residency	Frequency	Percentage
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Less than 1 year	1	2%
1-5 years	11	21.6%
5-10 years	10	19.6%
More than 10 years	29	56.9%

On Table 1.2, Only 1 respondent, or 2%, has lived in the community for less than a year. This suggests that very few participants are new residents, which means that most of the data collected is not influenced by individuals who are still unfamiliar with the community’s practices and environment.

There are 11 respondents, or 21.6%, who have stayed in the area for 1–5 years. This group represents individuals who have had enough time to observe and adapt to the community’s waste disposal practices. Their responses may reflect both initial impressions and gradually developed habits.

In addition, 10 respondents, or 19.6%, have lived in the community for 5–10 years. This indicates a moderate level of long-term exposure to local practices. Individuals in this group are likely to have established routines and a clearer understanding of how waste disposal is managed in their area.

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The majority of respondents, with 29 or 56.9%, have been living in the community for more than 10 years. This suggests that most participants are long-term residents who are highly familiar with the local environment and practices. Their responses are likely based on long-term observation and experience.

Overall, the data indicates that the majority of respondents have significant experience living in the community. This strengthens the reliability of the data, as most participants have a clear understanding of local waste disposal practices and their possible effects on waterways.

Table 1.3

Profile of the Respondents according to the Number of people living in the Household

Number of people living in the household	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	0	0%
3-5	27	52.9%
6-8	23	45.1%
More than 8	2	3.9%

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Table 1.3, there were no respondents who reported living in a household with only 1–2 members. This suggests that small household sizes are not common among the participants, and most households consist of more than two individuals.

A total of 27 respondents, or 52.9%, belong to households with 3–5 members. This indicates that the majority of respondents come from moderately sized households. In this type of household, waste generation is relatively balanced, and proper waste management practices are necessary to maintain cleanliness.

Meanwhile, 23 respondents, or 45.1%, reported living in households with 6–8 members. This shows that a large portion of respondents come from bigger households, which may generate more waste on a daily basis. As household size increases, the need for consistent and proper waste disposal practices also becomes more important.

Lastly, 2 respondents, or 3.9%, belong to households with more than 8 members. Although this group is small, it represents households with potentially high waste generation, which may require stricter waste management practices.

Overall, the data suggests that most respondents come from medium to large-sized households. This is important because household size can influence the amount of waste produced, highlighting the need for proper waste disposal practices to prevent environmental issues such as waterways pollution.

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Table 1.4

Profile of the Respondents according to their type of residency

Type of Residency	Frequency	Percentage
House (Owned)	38	76.5%
Apartment	4	7.8%
Rented house	9	17.6%
Informal Dwelling (Others)	0	0%

Table 1.4 shows the type of residency of the respondents. The results indicate that most of the respondents, with 38 or 76.5%, live in owned houses. This suggests that a large portion of the participants have stable living arrangements, which may contribute to a sense of security and comfort in their daily lives.

On the other hand, 9 respondents (17.6%) are living in rented houses, while 4 respondents (7.8%) reside in apartments. These findings show that only a small number of respondents depend on rental or apartment living. Furthermore, none of the respondents reported living in informal dwellings,

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indicating that all participants live in formal and established residential settings.

Overall, the data suggest that most respondents come from relatively stable residential environments, with home ownership being the most common type of residency among them.

Table 2.1

Segregation and Proper Disposal of Waste	4f	WM	3f	WM	2f	WM	1f	WM	Total f	Total WM	V.I.
1. I segregate my household waste into biodegr	11	0.86	15	0.88	21	0.82	4	0.07	51	2.63	HA / A

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adable, recyclable, and non-recyclable materials											
2. I dispose of my household waste in the proper collection bins or designated areas	22	1.72	24	1.41	3	0.11	2	0.03	51	3.27	VHA / SA

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3. I follow the community guidelines for proper waste disposal.	25	1.96	23	1.35	2	0.07	1	0.01	51	3.39	VHA / SA
4. I ensure that recyclable materials are separated before disposal	12	0.94	14	0.82	22	0.86	3	0.05	51	2.67	HA / A

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5. I encourage members of my household to practice proper waste segregation.	14	1.09	16	0.94	21	0.82	1	0.01	51	2.86	HA / A
Overall Weighted Mean (MW)										3.16	
Overall Verbal Interpretation										High Awareness / Agree	

Table 2.1 presents the respondents' level of awareness and practices regarding the segregation and proper disposal of waste. Based on the results,

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respondents generally demonstrate a high level of awareness and agreement with proper waste management practices, as reflected by the overall weighted mean of 3.16, interpreted as High Awareness / Agree.

Among the indicators, the statement “I follow the community guidelines for proper waste disposal” obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.39, with a verbal interpretation of Very High Awareness / Strongly Agree. This suggests that most respondents actively comply with community rules related to waste management. Similarly, disposing household waste in proper collection bins or designated areas also received a high rating with a weighted mean of 3.27, indicating strong adherence to proper disposal practices.

Meanwhile, statements related to waste segregation, such as separating biodegradable, recyclable, and non-recyclable materials (WM = 2.63) and ensuring recyclable materials are separated before disposal (WM = 2.67), were interpreted as High Awareness / Agree. This shows that respondents are generally knowledgeable and practice waste segregation, although not as strongly as compliance with disposal guidelines.

Additionally, encouraging household members to practice proper waste segregation obtained a weighted mean of 2.86, suggesting that respondents not only practice waste management individually but also promote responsible behavior within their households.

Overall, the findings indicate that respondents possess good awareness and positive practices regarding waste segregation and proper disposal, reflecting responsible environmental behavior within their community.

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Table 2.2

Frequen cy and Method of Waste Disposa l	4f	WM	3f	WM	2f	WM	1f	WM	Total f	Total WM	V.I.
6. I dispose of household waste regularly according to the community schedule	27	2.11	20	1.17	3	0.11	1	0.01	51	3.4	HA / A
7. I use environmentally	16	1.25	17	1	17	0.66	1	0.01	51	2.93	HA / A

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friendly methods for disposing of waste whenever possible											
8. I plan and manage my household waste to minimize unnecessary waste.	16	1.25	24	1.41	10	0.39	2	0.03	51	3.08	HA / A
9. I make sure that	21	1.64	23	1.35	6	0.23	2	0.03	51	3.25	VH A / SA

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household waste is properly stored before collection												
10. I try to reduce the amount of waste produced in my household.	23	1.80	22	1.29	5	0.19	1	0.01	51	3.29	VH A / SA	
Overall Weighted Mean (MW)										3.19		
Overall Verbal Interpretation										High Awareness /		

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	Agree
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Table 2.2 presents the respondents’ level of awareness and practices regarding the frequency and method of household waste disposal. The overall weighted mean of 3.19, interpreted as High Awareness/Agree, indicates that respondents generally practice proper waste disposal methods in their daily routines.

Among the indicators, the statements “I dispose of household waste regularly according to the community schedule” (WM = 3.40) and “I try to reduce the amount of waste produced in my household” (WM = 3.29) received the highest ratings, showing that most respondents consistently follow proper disposal schedules and are mindful of reducing waste. Additionally, proper storage of waste before collection (WM = 3.25) also showed a very high level of awareness, indicating responsible handling of waste within households.

On the other hand, using environmentally friendly methods for disposing of waste (WM = 2.93) received a slightly lower rating, although still interpreted as high awareness. This suggests that while respondents practice proper disposal, the use of eco-friendly methods is not as strongly observed. Overall, the findings show that respondents have good waste disposal habits, but there is still room for improvement in adopting more environmentally friendly practices.

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Table 2.3

Household Practices Contributing to Waterway Pollution	4f	WM	3f	WM	2f	WM	1f	WM	Total f	Total WM	V.I.
11. I avoid disposing of waste directly into rivers, canals, or drainage systems.	37	2.90	13	0.76	0	0	1	0.01	51	3.67	VHA / SA

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource**

12. I am aware that improper disposal of waste contributes to waterway pollution.	37	2.90	13	0.76	1	0.03	0	0	51	3.69	VHA / SA
13. My household practices prevent contamination of local water bodies	31	2.43	18	1.05	2	0.07	1	0.01	51	3.56	VHA / SA
14. I	36	2.82	11	0.6	3	0.1	1	0.01	51	3.54	VHA

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make sure that waste from my househol d does not reach drainage canals				4		1					/ SA
15. I properly dispose of waste to help keep nearby waterwa ys clean.	35	2.74	13	0.7 6	3	0.1 1	1	0.01	51	3.62	VHA / SA
Overall Weighted Mean (MW)										3.61	
Overall Verbal Interpretation										Very High	

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	Awareness / Strongly Agree
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Table 2.3 presents the respondents’ level of awareness regarding household practices that contribute to waterway pollution. The overall weighted mean of 3.61, interpreted as Very High Awareness/Strongly Agree, indicates that respondents are highly aware of how their household waste practices affect nearby waterways.

Among the indicators, the statement “I am aware that improper disposal of waste contributes to waterway pollution” obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.69, followed closely by “I avoid disposing of waste directly into rivers, canals, or drainage systems” (WM = 3.67). These results show that respondents clearly understand the negative impact of improper waste disposal and actively avoid harmful practices.

Other statements, such as preventing waste from reaching drainage canals (WM = 3.54) and ensuring household practices do not contaminate water bodies (WM = 3.56), also received very high ratings. This indicates strong awareness and responsible behavior among respondents in protecting waterways. Overall, the findings suggest that respondents are highly conscious of the effects of their actions on water pollution and demonstrate positive practices to help maintain clean and safe waterways.

Table 2.4

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Challenges and Barriers to Proper Waste Disposal	4f	WM	3f	WM	2f	WM	1f	WM	Total f	Total WM	V.I.
16.1 face challenges in following proper waste disposal practices due to lack of information or guidance	12	0.94	17	1	18	0.70	4	0.07	51	2.71	HA / A

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17. Accessibility to proper waste collection points affects my ability to dispose of waste properly .	1 1	0.8 7	20	1.17	17	0.6 6	3	0. 05	51	2.75	HA / A
18. I experience difficulties in managing waste due to limited	1 1	0.8 6	31	1.82	6	0.2 3	3	0. 05	51	2.96	HA / A

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space or resources at home											
19. Lack of waste segregation facilities in the community affects proper waste disposal	29	2.27	20	1.17	1	0.03	2	0.03	51	3.5	VH A / SA
20. Irregular garbage collection schedule	28	2.19	20	1.17	1	0.03	2	0.03	51	3.96	VH A / SA

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es affect my waste disposal practice s.												
Overall Weighted Mean (MW)											3.17	
Overall Verbal Interpretation											High Awareness / Agree	

Table 2.4 presents the respondents’ level of agreement regarding the challenges and barriers they encounter in practicing proper waste disposal. The overall weighted mean of 3.17, interpreted as High Awareness/Agree, indicates that respondents generally recognize and experience these challenges in their community.

Among the listed factors, irregular garbage collection schedules obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.96 (Very High Awareness/Strongly Agree), suggesting that inconsistency in waste collection is the most significant barrier affecting proper waste disposal practices. Similarly, the lack of waste segregation facilities in the community recorded a high weighted mean of 3.50 (Very High Awareness/Strongly Agree), indicating that inadequate infrastructure strongly influences improper waste management.

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Additionally, respondents also agreed that limited space or resources for managing waste (WM = 2.96) and accessibility to proper waste collection points (WM = 2.75) contribute to the difficulty in disposing of waste properly. These findings highlight logistical and environmental constraints experienced by the respondents.

On the other hand, lack of information or guidance on proper waste disposal practices received the lowest weighted mean of 2.71 (High Awareness/Agree), although it still indicates that this factor remains a concern among respondents.

Overall, the results suggest that while respondents are aware of proper waste disposal practices, systemic and environmental barriers—particularly irregular collection and lack of facilities—play a major role in limiting their ability to consistently practice proper waste management

Table 2.5

Awareness of Environmental Impact on Waterways	4f	WM	3f	WM	2f	WM	1f	WM	Total f	Total WM	V.I.

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21. I am aware that household waste directly affects rivers, lakes, and drainage systems.	37	2.90	13	0.76	1	0.03	0	0	51	3.96	VHA / SA
22. I believe that responsible waste management can prevent water pollution in my	36	2.82	12	0.70	2	0.07	1	0.01	51	3.6	VHA / SA

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communi ty.											
23. I actively participat e in communi ty program s that promote clean and safe waterwa ys.	6	0.4 7	20	1.1 7	17	0.66	9	0.1 7	51	2.47	HA / A
24. I understa nd that improper waste disposal	35	2.7 4	15	0.8 8	0	0	1	0.0 1	51	3.63	VHA / SA

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

can cause flooding and environmental damage												
25. I believe that community cooperation is important in protecting local waterways.	34	2.66	14	0.82	3	0.11	0	0	51	3.59	VHA / SA	
Overall Weighted Mean (MW)										3.46		

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Overall Verbal Interpretation	Very High Awareness / Strongly Agree
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Table 2.5 presents the respondents’ level of awareness regarding the environmental impact of waste on waterways. The overall weighted mean of 3.46, verbally interpreted as “Very High Awareness/Strongly Agree,” indicates that respondents possess a strong understanding of how waste affects aquatic environments.

Among the indicators, the statement “I am aware that household waste directly affects rivers, lakes, and drainage systems” obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.90, suggesting that respondents are highly conscious of the direct consequences of improper waste disposal. Similarly, the statements “I understand that improper waste disposal can cause flooding and environmental damage” (WM = 3.63), “I believe that responsible waste management can prevent water pollution in my community” (WM = 3.60), and “I believe that community cooperation is important in protecting local waterways” (WM = 3.59) were all rated at a very high level, further reinforcing the respondents’ strong environmental awareness.

However, the statement “I actively participate in community programs that promote clean and safe waterways” yielded a lower weighted mean of 2.47, interpreted as “High Awareness/Agree.” This suggests that although

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

respondents are knowledgeable and aware of environmental issues, their level of active participation in related initiatives is comparatively lower.

Overall, the findings reveal that while respondents demonstrate a very high level of environmental awareness, there exists a discrepancy between awareness and actual participation. This implies the need for interventions that not only sustain awareness but also encourage greater community involvement in environmental protection efforts.

Chi Square Test

This section presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between respondents’ demographic profiles, namely, role in the household, length of residency, household size, and the type of residency and their levels of awareness and household waste disposal practices; this suggests that disposal habits are not dictated by demographic factors pointing towards a generalized community behavior rather than one influenced by individual background.

Table 3

Demographic profile	Research variable	Chi square (χ^2)	P value	Interpretation
Role in the	Awareness	1.242	0.537	Not significant

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource**

household				
	Practice	0.855	0.652	Not significant
Length of residency	Awareness	1.568	0.667	Not significant
	Practice	3.759	0.289	Not significant
Number of people in the household	Awareness	0.823	0.844	Not significant
	Practice	1.762	0.623	Not significant
Type of residency	Awareness	2.045	0.360	Not significant
	Practice	0.535	0.765	Not significant

This table presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between respondents demographic profiles, namely, role in the household, length of residency, household size, and the type of residency and their levels of awareness and household waste disposal practices; this suggests that

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource**

disposal habits are not dictated by demographic factors pointing towards a generalized community behavior rather than one influenced by individual background.

Table 4

	High Practice	Low Practice	Total
High Awareness	32	14	46
Low Awareness	3	2	5
	35	16	51

Chi Square Statistics (χ^2): 0.134

P- value: 0.84

Significance Level: 0.05

This section examines the correlation between the residence level of awareness of environmental impacts and their actual household waste disposal practice; based on the result there is no statistically significant relationship between awareness and practice. This implies that while many residents are aware of the issue this awareness does not automatically result in high standard waste disposal practices suggesting that other factors such as resources or collection consistency may play a bigger role

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

The P-value of 0.84 is much higher than 0.05, there is no statistically significant relationship between awareness and practice in the specific group. In simpler terms having high awareness doesn't automatically mean the respondents are also doing high quality waste disposal practices.

Chapter V

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

Chapter 5 presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study. It highlights the key results regarding the level of community awareness on household waste disposal practices and their impact on waterway pollution. This chapter also interprets the significance of the findings and provides practical recommendations to improve waste management practices within the community.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study were summarized based on the statement of the problem.

1. Demographic Profile of Respondents in terms of:

1.1 Role in the Household

The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were classified as children within the household, followed by household heads and spouses. This indicates that younger household members comprised a significant

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

portion of the respondents, providing insights into household waste disposal awareness across different family roles.

1.2 Length of Residency in Barangay 174

Most respondents had resided in Barangay 174 for more than ten years, indicating a stable and well-established community population. The long-term residency of respondents suggests familiarity with local waste management systems and environmental conditions within the barangay.

1.3 Number of People Living in the Household

The majority of households consisted of three to five members, reflecting the common household structure in the community. This household size may influence waste generation patterns and disposal practices among residents.

1.4 Type of Residency

Most respondents reported living in owned houses, while fewer respondents resided in rented apartments or informal housing arrangements. This finding suggests relatively stable living conditions and long-term settlement within the community.

2. Level of Community Awareness in Household Waste Disposal Practices

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

2.1 Segregation and Proper Disposal of Waste

The overall weighted mean for segregation and proper disposal of waste was 2.63, verbally interpreted as Highly Aware. Respondents generally practiced proper waste segregation by separating biodegradable, recyclable, and non-recyclable materials and demonstrated compliance with established waste management guidelines. This indicates responsible waste management behavior among households.

2.2 Frequency and Method of Waste Disposal

The overall weighted mean indicated a high level of awareness and practice in terms of waste disposal frequency and methods. Respondents regularly disposed of household waste according to scheduled collection periods and ensured proper storage prior to disposal. However, environmentally friendly disposal alternatives obtained relatively lower weighted mean ratings, suggesting the need for improvement in sustainable waste management practices.

2.3 Household Practices Contributing to Waterway Pollution

The findings revealed a very high level of awareness regarding household practices contributing to waterway pollution. Respondents demonstrated strong recognition of the environmental consequences of improper waste disposal and reported avoiding practices that may contaminate rivers, canals, and drainage systems.

2.4 Challenges and Barriers to Proper Waste Disposal

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

The overall results indicated that respondents sometimes encountered challenges affecting proper waste disposal practices. The most frequently identified barriers included irregular garbage collection schedules and lack of adequate waste segregation facilities. Limited household space and accessibility to waste collection points were also identified as contributing factors influencing disposal behavior.

2.5 Awareness of Environmental Impact on Waterways

The findings indicated a very high level of environmental awareness among respondents. Participants acknowledged that improper waste disposal contributes to water pollution, flooding, and environmental degradation. Despite this awareness, participation in environmental programs and community initiatives was comparatively lower, indicating a gap between awareness and active engagement.

3. Significant Relationship Between Community Awareness and Demographic Profile

Statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between respondents' demographic profiles and their level of community awareness and household waste disposal practices at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that awareness and disposal behaviors are generally consistent across respondents regardless of household role, residency length, household size, or type of residence.

4. Significant Difference in the Level of Community Awareness on Household Practices Contributing to Waterway Pollution

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

The statistical results showed no significant difference in the level of community awareness regarding household practices contributing to waterway pollution. This finding suggests that respondents share similar levels of awareness and perceptions concerning environmental responsibility within the community.

5. Input for Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the results emphasize the need for strengthened community-based waste management programs, improved waste collection services, and increased environmental participation initiatives. Programs focusing on practical application of waste segregation, accessible disposal facilities, and sustained environmental education are recommended to bridge the gap between awareness and actual practice.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The demographic profile of the respondents indicates that most participants are long-term residents of Barangay 174, with the majority having lived in the community for more than ten years. Most respondents were identified as children within the household, followed by household heads and spouses. The majority of households consisted of three to five members and lived in owned houses, suggesting stable residency and established community living conditions.

College of Business and Accountancy
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

2. The study revealed that the community demonstrates a high level of awareness regarding proper household waste segregation and disposal practices. Respondents generally practice the separation of biodegradable, recyclable, and non-recyclable waste and follow the prescribed waste disposal guidelines in the barangay. These findings indicate that residents possess the knowledge and understanding necessary for responsible household waste management.
3. The findings show that respondents regularly follow community waste collection schedules and ensure proper waste storage prior to disposal. However, the use of environmentally friendly disposal methods is less emphasized, suggesting the need for further promotion of sustainable waste management practices.
4. The results indicate that the community has a very high level of awareness regarding the negative effects of improper waste disposal on waterways. Respondents recognize that poor waste management contributes to water pollution, flooding, and environmental degradation, and they report avoiding practices that could contaminate rivers, canals, and drainage systems.
5. Despite high awareness levels, respondents identified several barriers that hinder consistent proper waste disposal. The most significant challenges include irregular garbage collection schedules, lack of waste segregation facilities, limited household space, and accessibility

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

issues related to waste collection points. These external factors significantly influence the effectiveness of waste management practices within the community.

6. The study further found that participation in community environmental programs is relatively low, indicating a gap between environmental awareness and active community involvement. This suggests the need for stronger community engagement initiatives to encourage participation in environmental protection activities.
7. Statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between respondents' demographic profile and their level of awareness or waste disposal practices. This indicates that knowledge and practices related to waste management are generally shared across the community regardless of demographic characteristics.
8. Lastly, the findings showed no statistically significant relationship between community awareness and household waste disposal practices. This suggests that high environmental awareness alone does not guarantee consistent proper waste management, and that infrastructure, accessibility of facilities, and reliability of waste collection services play a crucial role in shaping household practices.

Overall, while the community of Barangay 174 demonstrates strong awareness and generally positive waste disposal practices, improvements in waste management infrastructure, collection services, and community

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Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource

participation programs are necessary to ensure consistent and sustainable environmental protection, particularly in preventing waterway pollution.

Recommendation

To enhance proper household waste disposal practices, it is recommended that local government units strengthen the implementation of waste segregation programs through regular monitoring and stricter enforcement of policies. Community-based information campaigns and educational seminars should be conducted to encourage active participation, not only awareness, among residents. Providing accessible and well-maintained waste collection facilities can also address barriers such as limited space and irregular garbage collection schedules. Additionally, promoting environmentally friendly alternatives, such as recycling and composting, can further improve sustainable waste management practices.

Moreover, collaboration between community leaders and residents should be encouraged to develop localized initiatives that address specific waste management challenges. Incentive programs may be introduced to motivate households to consistently practice proper waste disposal. Since the study revealed no significant difference across demographic profiles, interventions should be inclusive and applicable to all community members. Continuous evaluation and feedback mechanisms should also be established

College of Business and Accountancy
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to ensure the effectiveness of implemented programs and to foster long-term environmental responsibility.

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College of Business and Accountancy
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PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

Motivated BSBA HRM student with experience in administrative support and customer service, equipped with strong communication skills and a willingness to learn and grow.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Business Administration, Major in Human Resources Management	University of Caloocan City Expected Graduation: 2027
Senior High School - Humanities and Social Science	Vicente Malapitan Senior High School 2023
Junior High School	Camarin High School 2021
Elementary School	Camarin Elementary School 2017

CHARACTER REFERENCES

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I hereby certify that the above information is true and correct to the best of my knowledge and belief.

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PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

Motivated BSBA in Human Resource Management student with foundational knowledge in recruitment, employee relations, and administrative support, equipped with strong communication and interpersonal skills, and eager to learn, contribute, and grow in a professional environment.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Business Administration, Major in Human Resources Management	University of Caloocan City Expected Graduation: 2027
Senior High School - Accountancy, and Business Management	Lagro High School 2023
Junior High School	APEC Schools 2021
Elementary School	Villa Verde Elementary School 2017

CHARACTER REFERENCES

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PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

BSBA Human Resource Management student with a strong willingness to learn and grow in professional settings. Organized, dependable, and eager to contribute effectively in a team while developing new skills and gaining practical experience.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Business Administration, Major in Human Resources Management	University of Caloocan City Expected Graduation: 2027
Senior High School - Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics	Metropolitan Institute of Arts and Sciences 2023
Junior High School	Camarin High School 2021
Elementary School	Camarin Elementary School (Main) 2015

CHARACTER REFERENCES

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PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

A motivated individual seeking an opportunity to apply and enhance my administrative, customer service, and digital skills while contributing positively to the company's goals with professionalism, integrity, and strong work ethics.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Business Administration, Major in Human Resources Management	University of Caloocan City Expected Graduation: 2027
Senior High School - Accountancy, and Business Management	St. Clare College of Caloocan 2023
Junior High School	Tala High School 2021
Elementary School	Bagong Silang Elementary School 2017

CHARACTER REFERENCES

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I hereby certify that the above information is true and correct to the best of my knowledge and belief.

RINA JANE A. TAMBAGO
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VON JETRO IBANEZ

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PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

Motivated BSBA HRM student with experience in administrative support and customer service, equipped with strong communication skills and a willingness to learn and grow.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Business Administration, Major in Human Resources Management

University of Caloocan City
Expected Graduation: 2027

Senior High School - General Academic Strand

St. Vincent Institute of Technology: 2021

Junior High School

Manuel Luis Quezon Highschool
2021

Elementary School

Manuel Luis Quezon Elementary School
2017

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